

Heuristic Routing Algorithms for Minimum Energy Cooperative Multi-hop Wireless Networks

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Abstract— We investigate the minimum energy routing problem in cooperative multi-hop networks, where a single source communicates to a single destination assisted by several multi-hop relays that can accumulate information from retransmissions. Solving the minimum sum transmitter power problem for a multi-hop network implies finding the optimal resource allocation and transmission order (path). We address this problem by first deriving the *path weight* function which returns the minimum energy for given path. This function is found to admit a useful duality property which, basically, let us to define two recursive computations of the path weight using the intermediate path weights to each relay, either from the source (forward) or from the destination (backward). We propose new heuristics path discovering algorithms that make use of the duality property and are based on Dijkstra’s algorithm.

I. INTRODUCTION

Introducing relay capabilities in a network has a strong effect on the information flow that extends to all communication levels, from the achievable rate to the routing strategy. In the cooperative multi-hop (MH) network a single source communicates to a single destination assisted by several relay nodes that can *accumulate* the received energy/information from all the previous transmissions. Two main accumulative mechanisms have been considered in the literature: energy and mutual-information accumulation. Energy accumulation can be performed at the receiving nodes, e.g., through space-time coding or repetition coding [1], [2]. Mutual-information accumulation can be realized using rateless codes such as fountain and raptor codes. Accumulation mechanisms are considered in current and next generation standards since they increase communication reliability and reduce energy consumptions.

Related Work: Solving the minimum sum energy problem for a MH network implies finding the optimal resource allocation (power, bandwidth) and the optimal transmission order (path). For cooperative MH networks, this problem has been addressed in [1]–[6]. All these works considered the allcast cooperative (AC) multi-hop strategy where relay nodes are required to decode completely the source message. Although different scenarios were addressed in each of these works

(orthogonal transmissions in the low signal to noise (SNR) regime in [1], accumulated energy in [2], full-duplex nodes in [3], and orthogonal transmissions with fixed powers in [4]), the resource allocation problem, given a path, was shown to reduce to the same linear problem with linear constraints whose solution was found to be a simple recursive power-filling procedure. Instead, the optimal transmission order was shown in [2] and [1] to be a NP-complete problem and thus, only heuristic algorithms could be proposed.

Contributions: For the AC-MH network, we derive the power-rate *path weight* function which, given a path, provides the minimum sum power needed to obtain a desired rate. We show that the path weight can be computed recursively from the weight of the intermediate paths between the source and the relays (*forward* computation). More importantly, we show that the path weight satisfies a useful duality property which, basically, let us also to compute the weight of a path from the weight of the intermediate paths between the relays and the destination (*backward* computation). In addition, by combining the forward and backward path weight computation we find a very simple condition to decrease the weight of the path by removing nodes. This duality property is the basis of the optimal and heuristic routing algorithm proposed next. We use these two path weight computations and to propose new Dijkstra based heuristic algorithms to find good cooperative power-rate paths.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. The scenario is presented in Section II. In Section III, the cooperative power-rate path weight function is derived. Then, in Section IV, we propose Dijkstra based heuristic algorithms. Simulations results are shown in Section V. Finally, conclusions are drawn in Section VI.

II. SCENARIO

Consider a cooperative MH network where a single source communicates with a single destination assisted by L relays as depicted in Fig. 1 for $L = 3$. The “path” from the source to the destination is denoted with the set s of cardinality $|s| = L + 2$, where $s[0]$ and $s[L + 1]$ are the source and the destination, respectively. We use $s_{i,j} = \langle s[i], \dots, s[j] \rangle$ to denote the ordered subset of relays in s from node $s[i]$ to node $s[j]$. For the sake of simplicity, when there is no ambiguity on which path s we are referring to, we denote the i -th node in s simply as $[s]_i = i$. The channel gain from node $s[i]$ to node $s[j]$

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Fig. 1: Three-relay cooperative network model.

TABLE I: $c(R, \bar{P})$ and x_j depending on the scenario.

	x_j	$c(R, \bar{P})$	$\beta_{i,j}(s)$
FD Trans.	$\frac{P_j}{\bar{P}}$	$\frac{2^R - 1}{\bar{P}}$	$\alpha_{j,i}$
Low SNR	τ_j	$\frac{R}{\bar{P}}$	$\alpha_{j,i}$
Ort. Trans.	τ_j	$\frac{R}{\bar{P}}$	$\frac{\log(1 + \alpha_{j,i} \bar{P})}{\bar{P}}$

following the path s is denoted as $\alpha_{i,j}(s) \triangleq \alpha(s[i], s[j])$. We consider either simultaneous transmissions with full duplex nodes or orthogonal transmissions with half duplex nodes. For simultaneous transmissions, the source and relays transmit X_j for $j \in [0, 1, \dots, L]$ and, thus, each of the nodes $s[i]$ receives

$$Y_i = \sum_{j=0}^L \sqrt{\alpha_{j,i}} X_j + Z_i, \quad i = \{1, \dots, L+1\}. \quad (1)$$

We assume that signals X_i are independent, complex Gaussian random variables with zero mean and power P_i . The noise process at the relays and at the destination Z_i are complex independent white Gaussian, each one with zero mean and unit variance. Finally, $\bar{P} = \sum_{i=0}^L P_i$ is the sum transmitted power. For transmissions over orthogonal channels, we consider that node $s[i]$ only uses a fraction of the channel τ_i with $\sum_{j=0}^L \tau_j = 1$ to transmit X_i at a fixed power level $P_i = \bar{P}$. Notice that then $\bar{P} = \sum_{j=0}^L \bar{P} \tau_j$ and the received signal at node $s[i]$ during channel fraction τ_j is $Y_{ij} = \sqrt{\alpha_{j,i}} X_j + Z_i$, $i = \{1, \dots, L+1\}$.

We limit our analysis to the AC-MH transmission strategy [7] where relay nodes are required to decode completely the source message. We particularize this strategy to any scenario for which the optimum resource allocation problem for a given path is a linear problem. In particular, we consider: *i*) full duplex nodes *ii*) the low SNR, or *iii*) orthogonal transmissions with fixed transmitted powers. For any of these scenarios, given a path s , the cooperative rate-power $c(R, \bar{P})$ is defined by a set of rate-power conditions $c_i(\mathbf{x}) \triangleq \sum_{j=0}^{i-1} \beta_{j,i} x_j$ satisfying $c(R, \bar{P}) \leq \min_{i \in [1, \dots, L+1]} c_i(\mathbf{x})$ where c , x_j and $\beta_{i,j}(s) \triangleq \beta(s[i], s[j])$ depend on the scenario as shown in Table I.

III. THE PATH WEIGHT

In this section, we obtain the cooperative power-rate *path weight* function $w(s)$ which given a path s , provides the power-rate $\frac{1}{c(R, \bar{P})}$ as defined in Table I, at the optimal resource

allocation \mathbf{x}^* by solving

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{w(s)} &= \max_{\mathbf{x}} \min_{i \in \{1, \dots, L+1\}} c_i(\mathbf{x}) \\ \text{s.t.} \quad &\sum_{j=0}^L x_j = 1, \quad x_j > 0. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Before giving the solution to (2) in Theorem 1, we need to introduce some definitions and notation:

Definition 1: We define the *backward path weight* $\tilde{w}(\check{s})$ as the weight of the reverse path $\check{s} \triangleq \{s[L+1-i], i = 0, \dots, L+1\}$ if the elements in $\beta(s)$ are also reversed $\check{\beta}(\check{s}) \triangleq \{\check{\beta}_{i,j} = \beta_{L+1-j, L+1-i}, 0 \leq j < i \leq L+1\}$.

Definition 2: We define the *forward local path weight* $w_i(s) \triangleq w(s_{0,i})$ as the weight of the path $s_{0,i}$ from node $s[0]$ to node $s[i]$. Likewise, the *backward local path weight* $\tilde{w}_i(\check{s}) \triangleq \tilde{w}(\check{s}_{0,i})$ as the backward weight of the reverse path $\check{s}_{0,i}$ from node $\check{s}[0]$ to node $\check{s}[i]$ using the reverse gains $\check{\beta}(\check{s})$.

Definition 3 (Duality): We say that the path weight $w(s)$ satisfies duality as a function of the gains $\beta(s)$ if $w(s) = \tilde{w}(\check{s})$. Notice that if path weight satisfies duality and channel gains are symmetric then, the direct communication between a source and a destination using the path s and the feedback communication between the destination and the source using the reverse path \check{s} obtain the same path weight.

For simplicity, if the paths s or \check{s} are omitted, we assume that $\beta = \beta(s)$, $\check{\beta} = \check{\beta}(\check{s})$, $\beta_{i,j} = \beta_{i,j}(s)$, $\check{\beta}_{i,j} = \check{\beta}_{i,j}(\check{s})$, $w = w(s)$, $w_i = w_i(s)$ and $\tilde{w}_i = \tilde{w}_i(\check{s})$. Finally, we denote $\Delta_i = w_{i+1} - w_i$ and $\check{\Delta}_i = \tilde{w}_{i+1} - \tilde{w}_i$ and

Definition 4: We defined the *forward* and *backward feasible sets* of paths as

$$S = \{s : \Delta_i > 0, i = [0, \dots, L]\}, \quad (3a)$$

$$\check{S} = \{s : \check{\Delta}_i > 0, i = [0, \dots, L]\} \quad (3b)$$

and the intersection of these sets as the *feasible set* $\bar{S} = S \cap \check{S}$.

Then, the solution to (2) can be stated as follows:

Theorem 1: Only for paths $s \in \bar{S}$ all relays participate $x_i > 0, \forall i$. For these paths, the minimum power-rate ratio is given by $w(s) = w_{L+1}$ where the forward local path weights w_i can be computed recursively for $i = 1$ to $i = L+1$ as $w_i = w_{i-1} + \Delta_{i-1}$ ($w_0 = 0$) with

$$\beta_{i-1,i} \Delta_{i-1} = 1 - \sum_{j=0}^{i-2} \beta_{j,i} \Delta_j. \quad (4)$$

The optimal resource allocation is given by

$$x_i^* w(s) = \Delta_i, \quad i = [0, \dots, L]. \quad (5)$$

Proof: We omit this proof due to space constraints. It can be found in [8] available online. ■

According to (5) a positive amount of resources $x_i > 0$ is assigned to every node $s[i]$ in a forward only feasible path $s \in S$. Thus, any only forward feasible path $s \in S$ can be used to communicate the source with the destination using the resource allocation solution given by (5). All previous works addressing this problem, only required paths to belong to the forward feasible set. As far as we known, the condition for a path to also belong to the backward set \check{S} is first presented here

Algorithm 1 FB_Dijkstra's algorithm

$(p_o, l_o) = \text{FB_Dijkstra}(\mathcal{T}, w, o)$

- 1: **for** each node $t \in \mathcal{T}$ **do**
- 2: $l_{o,t} \leftarrow \infty; p_{o,t} \leftarrow \text{NIL}$
- 3: **end for**
- 4: $l_{o,o} \leftarrow 0; p_{o,o} \leftarrow \text{NIL}; \mathcal{R} \leftarrow \mathcal{T}$;
- 5: **while** $\mathcal{R} \neq \emptyset$ **do**
- 6: $u = \arg \min_{r \in \mathcal{R}} l_{o,r}$;
- 7: Extract u from \mathcal{R}
- 8: **for** each node $r \in \mathcal{R}$ **do**
- 9: compute $w_{u \oplus r} = w(p_{o,u} \oplus \langle u, r \rangle)$
- 10: **if** $l_{o,r} \succ w_{u \oplus r}$ and $w_{u \oplus r} \succ l_{o,u}$ **then**
- 11: $l_{o,r} \leftarrow w_{u \oplus r}; p_{o,r} \leftarrow \langle p_{o,u} \oplus \langle u, r \rangle \rangle$
- 12: **end if**
- 13: **end for**
- 14: **end while**

and is direct consequence of the duality property presented in next corollary.

Corollary 1: The path weight $w(s)$ in Theorem 1 satisfies duality as a function of the gains $\beta(s)$. Then, the path weight $w(s)$ can also be obtained as $w(s) = \tilde{w}(\tilde{s}) = \tilde{w}_{L+1}$ where the backward local path weights \tilde{w}_i can be computed recursively for $i = 1$ to $i = L + 1$ as $\tilde{w}_i = \tilde{w}_{i-1} + \tilde{\Delta}_{i-1}$ ($\tilde{w}_0 = 0$) with

$$\tilde{\beta}_{i-1,i} \tilde{\Delta}_{i-1} = 1 - \sum_{j=0}^{i-2} \tilde{\beta}_{j,i} \tilde{\Delta}_j. \quad (6)$$

Proof: We omit this proof due to space constraints. It can be found in [8] available online. ■

From the forward and backward local path weights, we can also establish the following useful relation between the path weight of s and that of $s^{(j)} \triangleq \langle s[0], \dots, s[j-1], s[j+1], \dots, s[L+1] \rangle$, where we have removed node $s[j]$.

Corollary 2: By removing node $s[j]$ from s , the difference in path weight $\tilde{\Delta}^{(j)} \triangleq w(s^{(j)}) - w(s)$ satisfies $\tilde{\Delta}^{(j)} = \Delta_j C^{(j)} \tilde{\Delta}_j$ with $\tilde{j} \triangleq L + 1 - j$ and $C^{(j)} = \frac{\beta_{j,j+1} \beta_{j-1,j}}{\beta_{j-1,j+1}}$.

Proof: We omit this proof due to space constraints. It can be found in [8] available online. ■

From Corollary 2, it is direct to see that given a feasible path $s \in \bar{S}$ we have $\tilde{\Delta}^{(j)} > 0$ and, consequently, a better path (lightest weight) can not be obtained by removing nodes. Later in Section IV, we make use of this corollary to propose heuristic routing algorithms that improve routes by removing or swapping nodes in a route.

IV. DIJKSTRA BASED HEURISTIC ALGORITHMS

Here, we first particularize Dijkstra's algorithm to use the forward or backward path weight computation and then propose heuristic routing protocols based on Dijkstra's algorithm.

A. The Forward/Backward Dijkstra's Algorithm

In Dijkstra's classical algorithm, given the set of all network nodes \mathcal{T} , the path weight function w , and the origin node of the search o , the algorithm returns the lightest paths $p_o = \{p_{o,t}, \forall t\}$ and weights $l_o = \{l_{o,t}, \forall t\}$ from node o to every

TABLE II: Heuristic Algorithms

Heuristic algorithms	
Scheduler	Optimal Path/Resources
DITH	SWRN RN
DITHADD{F,B}	
DIAC{F,B}	

node $t \in \mathcal{T}$. The pseudo code of Dijkstra's algorithm is shown in Algorithm 1. With the *forward* path weight, Dijkstra's algorithm obtains the lightest paths for the communication between the source and any node by setting $o = S$ and $w = w$. Instead, with a *backward* path weight, Dijkstra's algorithm obtains the reverse of the lightest paths for the communication between any node and the destination by setting $o = D$ and $w = \tilde{w}$. Then, the lightest path s^* can be obtained from \tilde{s}^* simply as $s^*[i] = \tilde{s}^*[L + 1 - i]$.

Dijkstra's classical algorithm assumes that the path sets S contains any path. From Theorem 1, we know that only forward and backward feasible paths $s \in \bar{S}$ can be optimal paths. Introducing in Algorithm 1, line 10, the condition $w_{u \oplus r} \succeq l_{o,u}$ or, equivalent, $w(p_{o,u} \oplus \langle u, r \rangle) \succeq w(p_{o,u})$, we are able to impose that only forward or backward feasible paths are consider if the forward or backward path weight are used.

B. Heuristic Algorithms

Most of the heuristic routing protocols proposed in the literature [1]–[4] for the AC-MH, as well as those proposed here, are based on decomposing the path discovering problem into two subproblems each of which can be solved efficiently. The first subproblem is to select the set of nodes that could participate in the transmission, here refereed to as the *schedule*. Then, the second subproblem is to specify a feasible order in which the scheduled nodes transmit (path) and finding the optimal resource allocation. A summary of the heuristic algorithm we consider is listed in Table II.

1) *Schedules:* For the first subproblem, we need to select *efficiently* a *good* schedule. At this point, we are mainly interested in ensuring the efficiency of the selection algorithm rather than on how *good* the schedule is. Merely, because we can only define approximately what a *good* schedule means. A *good* schedule is a set of nodes for which the second subproblem obtains a path with a light weight. Based on the related literature and the forward-backward duality result here presented, we propose several possible *good* schedules:

- i) DITH: Perhaps the simplest schedule we could consider is the lightest TH path s^{*TH} . As we know, this schedule can be found efficiently with Dijkstra's algorithm (DI) either forward or backward. The forward search is used by the CTNCR algorithm in [3], the SP algorithm in [2] and the Heuristic 1 in [9].
- ii) DITHADD{F,B}: In [4] and in Heuristic 2 algorithm in [9] authors proposed to add to the DITH schedule s^{*TH} all the nodes that are able to decode the message if the DITH schedule is used. Motivated by this solution, we propose a *forward* and *backward* schedule: For the forward (F) schedule s^{*THF} , we add to the DITH schedule s^{*TH} all the nodes with a lighter weight than the one at

Algorithm 2 Forward-Backward

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( $s$ )=FB( $w, \check{w}, s$ ):
1:  $f$ =false;  $\check{f}$ =false;  $j = 1$ ;  $i = 1$ 
2: while  $f$ =false or  $\check{f}$ =false do
3:   ( $s, f, l$ )=RN( $w, s, i$ )
4:    $f$ =true;  $i = |s| - 1$ ;  $j = \min(j, l)$ 
5:   ( $s, f, l$ )=RN( $\check{w}, s, j$ )
6:    $\check{f}$ =true;  $j = |s| - 1$ ;  $i = \min(i, l)$ 
7: end while

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the destination. Specifically, for $i = 1$ to $i = |s^{*TH}| - 1$, we construct s^{THF} by adding between nodes $s^{*TH}[i]$ and $s^{*TH}[i + 1]$ all the nodes $r \in \mathcal{R}/s^{*TH}$ satisfying $w(s_{0i}^{*TH} \oplus r) < w_{i+1}$. Instead, for the backward (B) schedule s^{THB} , for $j = 1$ to $j = |s^{*TH}| - 1$, we construct the reverse schedule \check{s}^{THB} , by adding between nodes $\check{s}^{*TH}[j]$ and $\check{s}^{*TH}[j + 1]$, all the nodes $r \in \mathcal{R}/s^{*TH}$ satisfying $\check{w}(s_{0j}^{*TH} \oplus r) < \check{w}_{j+1}$.

iii) **DIAC{F,B}**: The last schedules we propose are obtained by simply using the FB_Dijkstra's algorithm with the *forward* or with the *backward* path weight. These schedules are denoted as s^{ACF} and s^{ACB} , respectively. Notice that the forward and the backward schedules do not necessarily coincide and that they satisfy $s^{ACF} \in \bar{S}^{AC}$ and $s^{ACB} \in \check{S}^{AC}$.

2) *Feasible Order and Optimal Resource Allocation*: From Theorem 1, we know that the lightest path s^* must belong to the feasible set $s^* \in \bar{S}$. Then, we can easily compute the optimal resource allocation using (5). To find a feasible path $s \in \bar{S}$ from a non-feasible path $p \notin \bar{S}$, we simply remove every node $p[i]$ not satisfying the forward condition $w_{i+1} > w_i$ and every node $\check{p}[i]$ not satisfying the backward condition $\check{w}_{i+1} > \check{w}_i$ as describe in Algorithm 2. In the following proposition, we show that we can also guarantee that the feasible path $s \in \bar{S}$ found with Algorithm 2 is lighter than p under some conditions.

Proposition 1: Consider any path $p \notin \bar{S}$ with $p \in S$ or $p \in \check{S}$. Then Algorithm 2 finds a lighter feasible path $s \in \bar{S}$.

Proof: Consider the case of a path $p \in S$ (the same reasoning can be followed for any path $p \in \check{S}$). If node $p[j] = \check{p}[|p| - 1 - j]$ does not satisfy the backward condition $(w_{|p|-1-(j-1)} - w_{|p|-1-j}) < 0$, we known from Corollary 2, that by removing this node, we get a lighter path $p^{(j)}$ since then $w(p^{(j)}) - w(p) < 0$. After removing every node not satisfying the backward condition, the resultant path $d \in \check{S}$ might no longer belong to the forward feasible set $d \notin S$. However, since $d \in \check{S}$, we can get a lighter path by removing those nodes not satisfying the forward condition. By successively removing nodes until the path satisfies the backward and the forward condition, as described in Algorithm 2, we get the desired lightest path. ■

For each of the proposed *good* schedules, here we find a feasible transmission order (path).

i) The DITH schedule can be shown to be already a feasible path for the AC-MH and the CB networks $s^{*TH} \in \bar{S}^{AC}$, $s^{*TH} \in \check{S}^{CB}$.

Algorithm 3 Remove Nodes

```

( $s, f, l$ )=RN( $w, s, l$ ):
1:  $f$ =true;  $i = l$ 
2: while  $i \leq |s| - 1$  do
3:   if  $w_i > w_{i+1}$  then
4:     Remove node  $s[i]$  from  $s$ 
5:      $f$ =false;  $l = |s| - (i + 1)$ 
6:   else
7:      $i = i + 1$ 
8:   end if
9: end while

```

ii) **SWRN** for DIATHADDF,B schedules. These schedules do not necessarily satisfy the forward nor the backward conditions $s^{THF}, s^{THB} \notin S$ and $s^{THF}, s^{THB} \notin \check{S}$. For these schedules, we could find a feasible path by removing nodes (RN) using Algorithm 2. However, before removing any node it is convenient to give a good ordering to the additional nodes added to the DITH schedule. Motivated by the swapping (SW) solution proposed in [4], we can obtain a path in the forward feasible set $p^{THF} \in S$ from s^{THF} by swapping nodes $s^{THF}[i]$ with node $s^{THF}[i + 1]$ (or remove it if $i = L$) whenever the forward condition is not satisfied at node $s^{THF}[i]$. Once, we have $p^{THF} \in S$ we use Algorithm 2 to obtain a feasible path. Likewise, for the s^{THB} schedule we could swap nodes to obtain $p^{THB} \in \check{S}$ and, then find the feasible path by using Algorithm 2.

iii) **RN** for DIAC{F,B} schedules. These schedules satisfy $s^{ACF} \in S$ and $s^{ACB} \in \check{S}$ and thus, to obtain a feasible ordering $p^{ACF} \in \bar{S}$ and $p^{ACB} \in \check{S}$, we only need to remove nodes (RN) as described in Algorithm 2.

iv) Finally, we could always select the best path between the forward and the backward schedules. We denote these algorithms as DITHADD-F&B and DIAC-F&B

V. NUMERICAL RESULTS

We provide average and worst case results for the commonly used geometric propagation channel model. Then, the channel gain between nodes i and j is $\alpha_{ij} = d_{ij}^{-\nu}$ where d_{ij} is the distance between these two nodes and ν is the path-loss exponent. For each simulation case, we generate $M = 1000$ independent scenarios with $N = L + 2$ nodes randomly placed in a square plane of area $A = \frac{N}{\rho}$, where ρ [nodes/m²] stands for the density of nodes. For each scenario, we compute the path weights from every network node $i = [1, \dots, N]$ to every node $j \neq i$, assuming that the rest of nodes are potential relays. Unless otherwise stated we use $N = 10$, $\rho = 1$ and $\nu = 4$.

AC vs TH Multi-hop: First, let us illustrate the benefits of cooperation in MH communications by comparing the minimum power-rate path weight obtained with the traditional multi-hop (TH) against the one obtained with the AC-MH strategy. To speed up simulations, we use the path obtained with the DIAC+RN heuristic algorithm. Given a source-destination pair, we compute the ratio $\frac{w^{TH}}{w^{AC}}$ between the lightest TH path weight and the lightest AC path weights.

Fig. 2: Average $\frac{w^{TH}}{w^{AC}}$ as a function of \bar{P} , for $N = 10$, $\rho = 1$.

The ratio $\frac{w^{TH}}{w^{AC}} = \frac{c(R^{AC}, \bar{P}^{AC})}{c(R^{TH}, \bar{P}^{TH})}$, with $c(R, \bar{P})$ given in Table I depending on the scenario, is directly related to the cooperative power savings, given a fixed rate, as $\frac{\bar{P}^{TH}}{\bar{P}^{AC}} = \frac{w^{TH}}{w^{AC}}$ or to the cooperative rate gains, given a fixed power \bar{P} , as $\frac{R^{AC}}{R^{TH}} = \frac{w^{TH}}{w^{AC}}$ for orthogonal and low SNR transmissions and as $\frac{2^{\bar{R}^{AC}} - 1}{2^{\bar{R}^{TH}} - 1} = \frac{w^{TH}}{w^{AC}}$ for full duplex transmissions. We study the ratio $\frac{w^{TH}}{w^{AC}}$ as a function of \bar{P} assuming orthogonal transmissions scenario (notice that the results for full duplex transmissions and low SNR scenarios are those at $\bar{P} \rightarrow 0$). In Fig. 2, we show the maximum and the average ratio $\frac{w^{TH}}{w^{AC}}$ obtained. At low-medium \bar{P} levels, the gains of cooperation against multi-hopping are mainly found at medium-high \bar{P} levels $10 < \bar{P} < 30$ (dBs), there the gains are close to 20% in average and 70% at maximum.

Heuristics Algorithms: Next, we evaluate the heuristic path discovering algorithms presented in Section IV-B. Here, we only consider the case $\bar{P} \rightarrow 0$. First, in Fig. 3 we depict the percentage of success in finding the optimal path s^* as a function of the number of network nodes. We see that the FB_Dijkstra algorithm outperforms any of the path discovering algorithms based on improving the optimal TH path with very similar computational complexity. In addition, we can increase significantly the success probability simply by choosing the best path between the forward and the backward search (dashed lines). Then, focusing only on the scenarios for which the heuristic path s^{HE} does not coincide with the optimal path s^* , we show in Fig. 4 the average ratio between both path weights $\frac{w^{AC}(s^{HE})}{w^{AC}(s^*)}$ as a function of the network size.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we studied the minimum energy routing problem in cooperative multi-hop networks, which is known to be a NP-complete problem. We derive the power-rate *path weight* function and show that this function satisfies a duality property. Using this duality we define a cooperative forward and path weight computation. These path weight and the duality property are then used to propose new Dijkstra based heuristic routing algorithms for cooperative networks. It is shown that the gains of cooperation against multi-hopping can be of 20% in average and up to 70% at most. The best heuristic

Fig. 3: % success finding the optimal path, for $\rho = 1$, $\bar{P} \rightarrow 0$.

Fig. 4: Average ratio $\frac{w^{AC}(s^{HE})}{w^{AC}(s^*)}$ for $\rho = 1$, $\bar{P} \rightarrow 0$.

algorithms proposed are shown to find the optimal route with very high probability and if the optimal path is not found, the average loss is shown to be below 2% for networks with less than 15 nodes.

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